

Crypto-Antisemitism, a Barbadian Creole-Sephardic Testimony on Intolerance.

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Crypto-Antisemitism

Like the hidden nature of Crypto-Jews, Crypto-Antisemitism is a hidden variant of antisemitism that takes the masks of—whatever means is most socially acceptable for that particular environment. Antisemitism, and Crypto-Antisemitism are both intersectional, but Crypto-Antisemitism is hard to prove, ‘coincidental’ or purposefully enraging for Jewish people, to provoke a socially damaging Jewish response.

Crypto-Antisemitism can be intentional, or unintentional, in the same way that Crypto-Jewish traditions are practiced with or without consciousness.

When observing nations where, the immediate apprehension of Antisemitism is not observable, make note of intra-communal dynamics, and ask: How are Jewish people affected by these structures, and how can they be used against Jewish people?

Crypto-Antisemitism in the modern era is often enabled as an “opinion” and part of a “dialogue” when the expressed intention of such speech is to demonize a Jewish person in whatever means is easiest. Crypto-Antisemites likely realise that being publicly and easily identifiable as antisemitic will result in severe backlash, just as Jewish people have adapted to forced conversions, so too have antisemites adapted to the consequences for such

intolerance.

When Jewish people are provoked into providing a socially damaging response, this is when the Crypto-Antisemite is doing their work. The intention was never to make a valid statement or claim concerning any number of topics, it was to provoke rage, a response, or a suboptimal reaction to perpetuate a narrative of “irrational” Jews.

When this is done unintentionally, Jewish people are often left without a way to defend themselves, as the content and intention are not antisemitic, but the result and rhetoric are often identical and specific to antisemitic tropes; the main difference between this type of Crypto-Antisemitism and Antisemitism is the cultural relevance of the statements used to villainize Jewish people.

Note: This behavior operates as antisemitism, the person may or may not be intentionally antisemitic, Crypto-Antisemitism by default, refuses essentialism, and serves to declaim and provoke.

Introduction:

I frequently mention how, as a young child, my family would travel to different communities only to shortly thereafter be socially exiled from them. The term I am using, 'social exile' is very particular. I am referring to a mechanism wherein participating is met with enough hostility to make the participant not want to participate any further. Note, this is an intersectional perspective; this social mechanism crosses many domains, and thus it is speaking to not only sociology, but things such as gender studies, political and cultural dynamics, so on and so forth.

For instance, I believe that antisemitism does not have to be intentional, and it is a response to a specific cultural outline that Jewish people exhibit. For each Jewish person, this is incredibly personalized, unless reliance on anti-Semitic tropes occurs. Antisemitism, then, can be used in such a manner to perpetuate patriarchal societal norms. Being a woman who does not tolerate injustice—will frequently earn you the ire of men who do not like women who are not interested in subservience to men rather than G-d. So too, can antisemitism be racial, so too, can antisemitism be class-based, so too, can antisemitism be—Christian, Muslim, or any other religious denomination that villainizes the Jewish people.

Social Exile is: The exclusionary consequences of a lack of tolerance, especially when that lack of tolerance is socially hostile, defamatory, or theologically charged.

How is social exile tied to my Jewish identity?

An example, for censoring 'G-d', I was told I was afraid to mention the name of G-d, this person was either entirely unaware of Jewish norms because of a lack of exposure, or intentionally antisemitic, and I doubt the latter because they stated I was not Jewish, and this felt to be a declamation of my secular and queer advocacy. Leadership of that environment ultimately failed to call out the antisemitism that occurred, and instead made the implication that we were both in the wrong and needed to be civil.

Thus, soon thereafter, I left. This is social exile made manifest, and it started because I stated we did not need more G-d in governance. For the transgression of defending a secular constitution, I was then called a devil and defamed. Does this not sound familiar? In a Jewish state, 'G-d' in governance can mean any number of things, but in a post & neo-colonial society where politicians cater to Christian extremists? It means the persecution of what they deem to be 'heretics'.

But this extends beyond just that, and into queer spaces perpetuating hostile rhetoric toward Jewish people who do not conform to the "Anti-Zionist" "Anti-Israel" cultural position some Jews occupy. How can you make appearance in a queer communal environment when your friends despise you not for the contents of your character, but for the ancestral dream of return and reverence for the land of Judea.

And would they tolerate you if you deviated from the rhetoric they
publicize?

This is a broader pattern that has affected Jewish families since Crypto-Judaism was all but mandated within Portugal. It is not new, it was perfected within Iberia. This very structure still exists within contemporary society today, the difference is: It is much easier to claim it is not antisemitic if you wear another mask, like sexuality, gender, or a hatred for Israel.

My Experience with ‘nonexistent antisemitism and illustrious tolerance’.

In my experience, antisemitism is in response to cultural nodes Jewish people tend to exhibit, and it is always a tool of emotional ostracism, particularly when those nodes—ritual, critique, moral defiance—stand in tension with Christianized or colonial norms. As a young boy observing my mother, I noticed she would constantly have problems with others.

We were constantly being shamed out of ‘counter Christian communities’, and from what I know to be true, it had been because my mother is outspoken, and devoutly dedicated to studying the doctrine of G-d, even if she did not have the means to in a more traditionally ‘Jewish way’, given our ‘structurally deceased’ existence. It would be easy to blame my mother for

constantly being, or acting in such a manner, to perpetually end up despised and nearly universally hated across many spaces. While my mother is not perfect, she deserves the respect that many have not given earnestly to her.

Exemplary note:

Many within my society, especially within more fringe religious environments, visibly identify my mother as Jewish, though I can theorize as to why, I can only firmly say it is because she is of Sephardic descent, and I do recognize some similarities between Sephardic features, at least locally.

Interestingly enough, while my mother is accepted, I am frequently denied—and I strongly feel as if this is due to the efforts of the Mahamad to appear ‘white’, as I am a few shades down from my mother.

What allowed me to put together these dots of what had occurred in my childhood, is not only being exposed to more contemporary Jewish issues, educating myself on the nature of antisemitism, the inquisition, and religious ‘tolerance’ for Barbadian Jewry before the 1900s, 2000s, 2010s, and 2020s, but experiencing this ‘covert hatred’ first hand. For many, gender is rigid, neurodivergents are disliked, difference is disdained. Rejecting Christianity is seen as sin, women are to be subservient, men are to be strictly Christian-normative, heteronormative, and gender-normative. Homosexuality is despised, as is ‘difference.’

I have always been asked, “Are you from here?” told things like, “You trying to be great.” or “Did you go to private school?” Many assume because of my vernacular and method of speech, that I am not from Barbados, when I have been raised here my entire life, been educated in ‘depraved schools’, and

suffered all the abuse, harm, gaslighting, and stresses of being within the public education system. People do not culturally register me as “Barbadian” and if they do, because of how my mother raised me to be, they immediately equate my nature with being ‘unBarbadian’ or not poor.

And this does hurt, because by those I consider my countrymen, even before I had started taking hormone replacement therapy, I was not considered ‘part of the club’. And I, too, have weaponized this to my advantage. Typically, when I feel unsafe, I traverse the city with a Conservative Siddur Sim Shalom in hand that I borrowed from the Barbados Jewish Community, and I ensure the Hebrew is visible, it gives me strength—but it plays upon ‘foreignness’ as defensive mechanism. Though this may seem counterintuitive, I can assure you, very few would accost a person travelling with a visible Quran, wielding Arabic inscriptions. In this way, there is some overlap locally for religious minorities that speak different languages.

Foreignness within my society, in this way, invokes questions, pauses, and consequence evaluation, but conformity? “Assimilation?” It results in abuse because the expectation is to follow majoritarian societal norms; regardless, assimilation does not work; it could be for ancestry, it could be for expression, it could be for culture, it could be to perpetuate corruption, many are genuinely wired to disdain parts of Jewish life which are foreign to them because antisemitism is a response to Jewish people, our identities and our culture, rather than a vague concept of being hated for no reason. Jewish people are disdained for not conforming to majoritarian societal norms, and that is why Israel must exist.

Things that we as a community have developed throughout thousands of years, Jewish Philosophy, Divinely mandated rebellion, a rigorous quest for democracy, and fair treatment under majoritarian rule. There are many things, we as a community, family, and individually have developed due to our lineage's experiences, be it creolization, the inquisition, war, the holocaust, pogroms, blood libels, expulsions from our homes, and much more. Yet, antisemites see us as simply "Jews", "problem makers", "money hoarding elites", so on and so forth, without acknowledging our humanity and the pains we have endured vis-à-vis collective punishment for religious difference.

In that same breath, there are Jews who are tolerated by bigots only so far as it is convenient and easily co-optable for their own aims when majoritarian conformity is exhibited, popular examples of this are figures like Ben Shapiro, who has stated things such as "Homosexuality is sin", a Christian-understood way of communicating halachic norms concerning sexuality. Ben Shapiro has nearly exclusively been educated within Jewish environments; surely he can mention the structural implications for all Jews, including converts, if he proclaims divergent love to be against G-d's law.

It would mean, queers are not living a Jewish life, thus cannot convert, thus cannot claim they are identified as Jewish, thus experience major rejections from important and integral functions within Jewish communal life, why is it I must observe that many reformist synagogues and educational environments have disclaimers that "you will not be accepted by all Jewish people if you convert in such a way" yet the Torah tells us to love Converts as any other Jew? What appears to me is that only certain types of Jews are

provided with unequivocal acceptance.

‘Spiritually undocumented’ Crypto-Jewish inheritance

Spiritually undocumented refers to individuals or families whose Jewish identity persists through practice, memory, or persecution, but who are denied recognition due to disrupted maternal lineage or forced assimilation under coercive historical regimes.

In the eyes of many, a family that has broken the maternal line of documented and verifiable worship—is no longer Jewish, yet still, many gentiles treated us like dogs sometimes being entirely unaware of the Jewish undertones within my family, and did things they would not in good conscience have done to others, and they had not, at least whilst we were there. These conflicts had always come from above, down onto us; never once was it “punching up.” A pastor is behaving inappropriately toward a relative, my mother does not allow it toward herself or her children, and the result? It is a sermon decrying us without specifically mentioning our names.

You see, it was never really about G-d or the nature of my mother’s criticism of pastoral doctrine and actions; it was about using whatever means that can be used to villainize us, shame us, and make us leave. If my mother is expressing divergent religious thought in an environment that does not tolerate it, that is the method of approach they will use to justify hatred of

her, and that hatred is antisemitic, even if it does not know that it is.

My mother knew that these pastors meant us, and in retrospect, it was pronounced when you speak of ‘corrupting the word of G-d’, basically a modern-day ‘heresy’ accusation, one that would have gotten us burnt to death or beaten in olden times. But because our society is not violent within religious spaces because decorum and respectability take precedent within the house of G-d, instances like this are entirely disregarded as genuine antisemitism by those who are unaware of the mutating disease of Jew-hate.

Though I believe many simply disdain what they cannot control, nor understand, thus the result is antisemitism, even if not intentionally targeted toward Jewish people.

For my family, engagement in religious Christian but traditionally Jewish environments was awful; we were not in tune with others, even if they practiced Hebraic traditions and biblical literalism, they did not like to be questioned or exposed to divergent interpretations. The only groups we found extensive refuge within were the Jehova’s witnesses, and 7th day Adventists, though these did not last due to communal issues, some of which were not antisemitic in nature, but exploitative and immoral; it would have been difficult to continue after what had occurred.

Intra-communal dynamics

The reality is that orthodoxy is culturally dominant, and it emphasizes strict halachic observance. For those invested in rigid interpretations of Jewish law, because my grandfather publicly proclaimed Catholicism and my grandmother was secular, structurally, we are not Jewish. But? In that same breath, the question is whether a transgender person could live a Jewish life and have their gender affirmed; thus, is a conversion of 'return' valid beneath the gaze of such eyes? What would be the point of going through such a ritual, only to be alienated, or denied from the 'identifiably' of normative Jewish worship'. I've found Ashkenormative environments rarely speak to the racial, sexual, gendered, and 'divergent worship intolerant' nature of some periods within Jewish history, as well as the modern day, unless they are Heterodox, and even then? It depends on communal leadership to address reality rather than speak to easily digestible narratives.

This is a self-destructive and corrosive cycle. If more strict religious observance is the mandate of existence, then what is left for us Jews who are disenfranchised and rejected not only by our people, but those who seek to harm us? Where are we supposed to go? And what are we supposed to do? Exclusion of halachically divergent identities for me means that I am not considered 'fully' Jewish in the same way I am not considered 'fully' Indian, or 'fully black.' And for some, that means I am not Jewish at all, rather "Jewish adjacent" I reject these notions unequivocally, I am not 'some things' I am everything and made in the divine image. While I can weather this storm because I know, and I've seen that it is much worse elsewhere, and I am religious, not many are willing to, and that has consequences for descendants

who wish to break the cycle of enforced norms that stall social and cultural progression.

Additionally, the weight placed upon Conversion understates Jewish heritage, to make it irrelevant, and those who have Jewish heritage, rather than observable conformity to traditional Jewish norms—less Jewish than those with the blood of Jews within their veins. Nazi eugenics were little to do with religious observance, and everything to do with relegating Jewish heritage to subhuman, and insufficient.

I do not believe, and I will never allow myself to be told that the standard for being Jewish is entirely due to one's ability, and their family's ability to maintain aspects of Jewish law which actively did not suit their lifestyle, due to any number of divergent and non-traditional reasons. My mother is a Jew, she believes in Christ. I am a Jew, I do not believe in Christ. My grandfather and grandmother were both Jews, and they had their own identities, their own struggles, trauma and their own pressures as members of society. None of us has ever been "traditionally Jewish", and how could we be? We are a small minority whose family members typically immigrate out of the country and leave us behind. We are not the educated or rich ones who can do better, we are the ones who must remain, and we have different pressures to conform than others who leave a Christian Majoritarian post-colonial society for the Religious freedoms of the United Kingdom, Canada, or America.

Assertions:

Crypto-Jewish inheritance cannot, and must not, be judged by those not privy to Crypto-Jewish circumstances. I reject and declaim the notion that a Crypto-Jew must return or convert to normative Judaism to be accepted and recognized as religiously Jewish. However, I deeply believe in communal engagement, Jewish education, and commitment to our people.

I have grown disillusioned with the narrative that my heritage is not Jewish enough because of Christian assimilation, I have “Christian names” on secular documents because this is how our society functions, these are not isolated remnants, but realities, and if a Jewish person decides to worship something that is not normative, but within the spirit of Judaism, it is not for bureaucratic officials to determine if that is religiously valid.

The only ‘return’ or ‘conversion’ I will ever part-take in, if I choose to, will be reformist, and I will not care if it is recognized or not.

Encore: A news article containing my Grandfather, Lance Neville King (II), in 1952

Camp Fire

The St. Patrick's Scout Troop held a Camp Fire at St. Patrick's School yard on Monday night under the patronage of Rev. Fr. A. Parkinson. It was in aid of Scout Funds. Two Scouts, B. Dempster and L. N. King were responsible for keeping the Camp Fire burning. Another Scout, D. Carter, entertained those present with songs, jokes and sketches. He was loudly applauded.

David Carter sang ten songs. His best was "The Hungry Man From Clapham." To please the crowd, he had to sing this on three occasions.

There were four recitations by Scouts E. Joseph, J. Joseph, A. Phillips and G. St. Louis. F. Hyppolite sang "Song of Songs" and "Blue Berry Hill." After two hours of entertainment, the audience sang the Scout Hymn and the National Anthem.

Among those present were: Father A. Parkinson, Father Morrison, Scout Master S. Flemming, Assistant Scout Master Hutson, Club Master H. Blackett, Messrs. H. W. Clyne, C. Blackett, G. Welsay, W. Grace, C. Blackett, R. Jarvis, Mr. E. Jarvis, Miss E. Kelly, Mrs. Lavine, Mr. P. Persil, Mr. F.

Hyppolite, Mrs. Hyppolite, Mrs. Williams, Mr. L. R. Fernandes and Mr. Gill.

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